

A Shared Telemanipulation Interface to Facilitate Bimanual Grasping and Transportation of Objects of Unknown Mass

Davide Torielli^{1,2}, Luca Muratore¹, Alessio De Luca^{1,2}, and Nikos Tsagarakis¹

Abstract—The teleoperation of robots with human-like capabilities may pose significant challenges to the human operator due to the kinematic complexity and redundancy of these robots. Bimanual telemanipulation represents such a challenging task that requires precise coordination of the two arms to perform a stable bimanual grasp on an object and eventually transport the object while maintaining the grasp.

In this work, we present a shared control telemanipulation interface to facilitate the bimanual grasping and transportation of objects of unknown mass. With the proposed method, the robot is able to transport the object maintaining autonomously a sufficient amount of grasping force while accepting commands from the operator to reach the desired location. As humans do, it is not necessary to know the weight of the object in advance; instead, the robot estimates it during the lifting phase. On the basis of the estimated weight, the required amount of grasping force is computed. During object transportation, the robot autonomously regulates the grasping forces in a shared control fashion, allowing the operator to seamlessly command only the trajectories of the object.

The proposed method has been implemented and validated on the CENTAURO robot, a quadrupedal platform with a humanoid dual arm upper body, performing experiment where objects of different weights and dimensions must be picked up and transported.

I. INTRODUCTION

Increasing trends in robotics show how the world is expecting to have robots always more capable of assisting and even replacing human workers in tasks that are exhausting, repetitive, and dangerous. Since robots are supposed to deal with environments originally intended for humans, it is important to have systems with human-like form, to provide capabilities similar to those of a human worker [1]. Following these trends, several dual arm humanoid and mobile robots have been developed in recent years [2]–[4], allowing to perform bimanual manipulation tasks. According to [5], dual arm manipulation can be divided into non-coordinated manipulation, where the two arms perform different tasks, and coordinated manipulation, where the arms are dedicated to the same task. Among the coordinated

Fig. 1. The CENTAURO robot is teleoperated to place a block inside a container. The experiment is described in Section IV.

classification, bimanual manipulation is defined as physically interacting with the same object, e.g., for grasping and transporting a large and heavy load, which a single arm can not deal with. Different control laws have been proposed to face bimanual pick and place tasks, such as hybrid force/position [6], [7], impedance [8], and admittance control [9]–[11]. The bimanual task has often been tackled considering a cooperative task space formulation [12], which allows to extend the principles of single manipulators to the combined dual arm system, using meaningful relative and absolute variables and solving the kinematic problem with Jacobian matrices [13]–[16]. In telemanipulation, it is often necessary to include autonomy modules in the human-robot teleoperation interface to perform bimanual tasks that are otherwise not addressable. For example, shared control and shared autonomy techniques [17] can help the operator to grasp a particular object and to maintain the grasp while manipulating it [18], [19]. Other approaches exploit the concept of task priority, which ensures that high-priority tasks are satisfied without being affected by low-priority ones. Bimanual object transportation tasks can be tackled considering as the highest priority task the object grasping constraint, while lower priority tasks may consider joint limits [20], manipulability [21], or other specific objectives relevant to the application, like the yaw attitude of floating platforms [22].

A particular challenge to face is how to deal with unknown objects. When humans perform a bimanual transportation of an object, they rely on a very amazing sensory system (i.e. visual information combined with the sense of touch) to

*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101016007 CONCERT and grant agreement No. 871237 SOPHIA, and the Italian Fondo per la Crescita Sostenibile - Sportello "Fabbrica intelligente", PON I&C 2014 - 2020, project number F/190042/01-03/X44 RELAX.

¹Davide Torielli, Luca Muratore, Alessio De Luca and Nikos Tsagarakis are with Humanoids and Human Centered Mechatronics (HHCM), Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genova, Italy davide.torielli@iit.it, luca.muratore@iit.it, alessio.deluca@iit.it, nikos.tsagarakis@iit.it

²Davide Torielli and Alessio De Luca are also with Department of Informatics, Bioengineering, Robotics, and Systems Engineering (DIBRIS), University of Genova, Genova, Italy

adapt the grasping forces depending on the contact and forces information perceived. By exploiting this multimodal perception, humans manage to perceive and estimate the mass of an object and adapt accordingly the forces they apply as needed to ensure the bimanual grasp. In robotics, estimating the object mass and, in general, the object inertia parameters are still big challenges, tackled in different ways by past works. In a recent survey [23], the authors describe different techniques divided into: (1) purely visual methods [24], (2) exploratory methods in which basic interactions with the object are performed (e.g., little strikes [25] or tilts [26]), and (3) fixed-object methods, where the object is fixed with respect to the end-effector(s), e.g. it is already grasped [27].

All the above mentioned works show that there is the necessity of teleoperation interfaces capable of assisting and facilitating the human operator in the execution of such difficult tasks. In this regard, our previous work [28] introduced the concept of TelePhysicalOperation, a human-robot teleoperation interface targeting to control intuitively highly redundant robotic platforms. In this work, we further enhance our interface by introducing an autonomous functionality to facilitate the teleoperation of pick-and-place operations of boxes with different sizes, eliminating the need for the operator to perceive directly the interaction forces in order to perform such a task. Haptic feedback solutions do exist [29] but they augment the complexity of the operator interface, the force feedback fidelity and transparency is far from being realistic, and false forces may even complicate more such an operation. Therefore, instead of providing force sensor information to the operator, our solution adds a certain amount of robot autonomy in the teleoperation interface following the shared control concept. The proposed interface enables the robot to automatically reach and grasp the object of interest with the two arms and to maintain a stable grasp while the object velocities are commanded by the operator. The unknown object mass is calculated from the estimated forces at the end-effectors. This information is used to modulate the grasping forces as required to maintain the grasp and transport the object safely without applying extended forces, which could damage the object. The operator is able to teleoperate the robot by commanding the velocities of the bimanually grasped object to transport it to the desired location without taking care about the maintenance of grasping contacts and applied forces. We have experimentally demonstrated the proposed autonomous feature with a number of tasks performed by the CENTAURO robot [2], a hybrid leg-wheel system with an anthropomorphic upper body (Fig. 1).

The paper is structured as follows: in Section II we present our telemanipulation interface; in Section III we describe the technical details of the object mass estimation, the grasping force computation, and the object transportation; in Section IV we validate our approach with a series of experiments; finally in Section V conclusions are drawn.

II. TELEPHYSICAL OPERATION APPLICATION TO BIMANUAL TASKS

In our previous work, we have presented the TelePhysicalOperation concept [28], a novel teleoperation architecture that resembles the “marionette” type of interface. This interface permits to apply virtual forces on selected robot body parts resembling a real human-robot interaction during collaborative/teaching tasks. These virtual forces are taken into account by the robot, which will generate motions accordingly, as in the case of a physical human-robot interaction where the human is applying the forces to the robot body to adjust its posture and to guide its end-effector. The result is an architecture which maintains the intuitiveness of the human-robot physical interaction, but also includes the safety of interacting and operating robots from a distance.

With mobile manipulation platforms, the virtual forces can be applied to the mobile robot body other than to the arm(s), allowing to remotely control both the mobility and the manipulation of the robot. This is possible by changing the control point where the virtual force is applied, a procedure that may be repetitive and may increase the execution time for some tasks. In fact, in [30], we introduced an autonomous functionality that considers the robot arm manipulability measure (i.e., the velocity transmission ratio [31]), to distribute the virtual force applied by the human operator through the TelePhysicalOperation interface to the robot end-effector and to the mobile base according to the level of the arm manipulability. If the manipulability of the arm begins to decrease significantly, e.g. the arm is stretched, the operator command on the end-effector will generate mobile base motions instead of arm motions.

In [30], we have demonstrated the effectiveness of this manipulability-aware shared locomanipulation in a bimanual pick-and-place task. One common problem of such kind of tasks is that the operator may not be aware of the forces applied on the object to be transported. Therefore, it may happen that the robot does not apply enough grasping forces, making the object slip and fall, or it applies very high grasping forces, using more effort than necessary to handle an object. Hence, in this work, we propose a shared control method to let the robot grasp and manipulate the object with the required amount of grasping force. This grasping force permits to keep the grasp on the object while accepting commands from the operator to transport it. This permits to the operator to only take care about commanding the object velocities, and not about the necessary arms movements needed to hold the object without losing the contacts or damaging it due to the extensive forces applied.

In detail, the proposed method is based on the following features, schematized in Fig. 2:

- The *object mass estimation*. This feature permits to estimate the mass of the object, based on the forces sensed by the robot end-effectors.
- The *grasping force computation*. From the estimated mass the required grasping force is derived such that the robot will apply only the necessary level of forces

Fig. 2. Logic scheme of the proposed telemanipulation interface. In a preliminary phase (top left colored area), the object mass estimation \hat{m} is derived from the end-effector sensed forces f_s . From \hat{m} , a required grasping force \bar{f} is computed. During the transportation phase (right-bottom colored area), the operator commands the object velocities \dot{x}^* while the robot maintains a stable grasp adapting the sensed force to the computed grasping force \bar{f} .

to transport the object, without applying too high forces that could damage the object or the robot itself.

- The *object transportation control interface*. This transportation control interface allows to transport the object in such a way that the operator is not required to consider the constraint imposed by the grasping. He can just generate reference velocities for the grasped object to drive it into the desired location, without taking care about how the arms or the mobile base should move to reach the target goal.

The mass estimation and the subsequent derivation of the grasping force computation rely on a force estimation module based on the residual method [32] and the use of the Coulomb's law of friction [33], [34]. Finally, the manipulability-aware shared locomanipulation feature of the previous mentioned work [30] has been integrated to transparently distribute the operator command related to velocity of the bimanually grasped object on the arms and on the mobile base, combining the mobility and the arms motions during the transportation of the object.

III. SHARED TELEMANIPULATION INTERFACE FOR OBJECT BIMANUAL GRASPING AND TRANSPORTATION

In this section we detail the shared control telemanipulation method applied in a bimanual pick and transport task, presenting the technical details of the three features introduced in Section II. We consider a scenario in which the arms of the robot have reached the sides of the object of an unknown mass. We assume that the nature of the object allows the robot to grasp and transport it by establishing contacts and applying forces on two opposing sides and by considering only linear forces (i.e., no torques). In the first phase, the robot grasps the object applying an initial level of grasping force and lifts it. In this phase the initial level of grasping force must be put sufficiently high by the operator to lift the object firmly. Once the object is lifted from its support, its mass is estimated on the basis of the sensed

Fig. 3. Forces involved in the mass estimation formulas of Section III-A.

forces at the end-effectors. Based on the estimation of the mass, a required grasping force is derived and commanded to the two robot arms to permit the transportation without slipping and without applying an unnecessary amount of force. After this phase, the operator can command object velocities to transport the load safely to a desired location. This procedure resembles what humans sometimes do in front of an object of unknown mass, i.e., they modulate the force necessary to keep the object after its mass is estimated during the lifting phase. The details of the shared control telemanipulation method that addresses the above scenario are presented in the following subsections.

A. Object Mass Estimation

The component of the proposed shared telemanipulation control involves the estimation of the object mass. Taking into account the object frame with the z axis perpendicular to the ground, we assume that the contact points where the robot end-effectors apply forces to the object are at the same height on the z axis. Furthermore, we consider that a sufficiently high level of initial grasping force is applied in the first phase to permit to lift the object. In such conditions, after the object has been lifted from its support, in the absence of slip and external disturbances, the gravitational force f_g is equal to the sum of the two end-effectors sensed forces along the z axis direction:

$$f_g = [f_{s,l}]_z + [f_{s,r}]_z \quad (1)$$

Fig. 4. Forces involved in the grasping force computation formulas of Section III-B.

where $[\mathbf{f}_{s,l}]_z$ and $[\mathbf{f}_{s,r}]_z$ are the z axis component of the sensed forces of the left and right end-effectors. From Newton's second law applied to gravity, $f_g = mg$, we can compute the estimated mass \bar{m} as:

$$\bar{m} = \frac{1}{g} \left([\mathbf{f}_{s,l}]_z + [\mathbf{f}_{s,r}]_z \right) \quad (2)$$

where g is the gravity acceleration. A scheme of the forces involved in these formulas is depicted in Fig. 3. The mass estimation is performed by averaging the estimated mass values computed from a certain number of sensed force samples, in order to decrease the influence of the noise of the force estimation.

B. Grasping Force Computation

After estimating the mass of the object, the method computes the required grasping force that permits to maintain a stable grasp by counterbalancing the gravity force $f_g = mg$ with the friction forces at the contact points:

$$f_{f,l} + f_{f,r} = mg \quad (3)$$

where $f_{f,l}$ and $f_{f,r}$ are the Coulomb friction forces generated by the normal grasping forces $f_{N,l}$ and $f_{N,r}$ applied by the two robot end-effectors. Given the Coulomb friction law $f_f \leq \mu_s f_N$, with μ_s the static friction coefficient, it can be obtained what follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_s f_{N,l} + \mu_s f_{N,r} &\geq f_{f,l} + f_{f,r} = mg \\ f_{N,l} + f_{N,r} &\geq \mu_s^{-1} mg \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where it is assumed that the friction coefficient is the same at both contact points. A scheme with the relevant quantities involved is present in Fig. 4. Given the above, the required grasping force \bar{f} for each end-effector can be computed as:

$$\bar{f} = k \left(\frac{\bar{m}g}{2\mu_s} \right) \quad (5)$$

where $k > 1$ is a safety margin gain used to take into account errors such as in the measurement of the sensed forces \mathbf{f}_s , and any uncertainties in the static friction coefficient μ_s . Having computed the required grasping force, the robot arms then regulate the grasping forces applied by the end-effectors from the initial force level (used during the lifting phase) to the required grasping force level \bar{f} .

Fig. 5. Scheme of the relevant vectors involved in the object transportation control interface formulas of Section III-C.

C. Object Transportation Control Interface

Once the object is grasped and the required grasping force \bar{f} is applied, the operator can control the robot by directly commanding the velocity of the bimanual grasped object while the grasping of the object is maintained in an autonomous manner by the telemanipulation shared control, which generates the forces necessary to keep the grasp stable. From [10], which uses the principle of virtual sticks of [6], and the cooperative task representation of [12], we compute the Cartesian linear velocity commands $\dot{\mathbf{x}}_j \in \mathbb{R}^3$, with $j = l, r$ for the left and right end-effectors with the following admittance control formula:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_j = \dot{\mathbf{x}}^* + \mathbf{D}^{-1} (\mathbf{R}_b ({}^b \mathbf{f}_{s,j} - {}^b \mathbf{f}_{d,j}) + \mathbf{K} (\mathbf{p}_{d,j} - \mathbf{p}_j)) \quad (6)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{x}}^*$ is the object linear velocity command imposed by the operator, $\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ are diagonal matrices of damping and stiffness, $\mathbf{f}_{s,j}, \mathbf{f}_{d,j} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}$ are the estimated and the desired force at the j end-effector, $\mathbf{p}_j, \mathbf{p}_{d,j} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}$ are the actual position and the desired position of the j end-effector, and $\mathbf{R}_b \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the rotation matrix from object frame $\langle b \rangle$ to the reference frame. The y axis of the object frame $\langle b \rangle$ lies in the line which connects the two end-effectors (Fig. 5); hence the rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_b is necessary because the required grasping force \bar{f} is referred to the frame $\langle b \rangle$. The desired force $\mathbf{f}_{d,j}$ for each end-effector j is set as:

$$\begin{aligned} {}^b \mathbf{f}_{d,l} &= [[{}^b \mathbf{f}_{s,l}]_x, \bar{f}, [{}^b \mathbf{f}_{s,l}]_z]^T \\ {}^b \mathbf{f}_{d,r} &= [[{}^b \mathbf{f}_{s,r}]_x, -\bar{f}, [{}^b \mathbf{f}_{s,r}]_z]^T \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where \bar{f} is the required grasping force of Eq. (5) applied along the direction normal to the contact surfaces of the object. The signs of the y component of the desired forces ${}^b \mathbf{f}_{d,l}$ and ${}^b \mathbf{f}_{d,r}$ are set accordingly to the chosen reference frame. Instead, the x and z components are set equal to the respective components of the sensed force.

Furthermore, to help in maintaining a stable grasp, we have chosen a simple leader-follower concept where one arm (e.g., the right arm r) follows the leader one (e.g., the left arm l). Therefore, in Eq. (6) we have considered the Cartesian linear position error of the end-effectors, where the desired positions $\mathbf{p}_{d,l}$ and $\mathbf{p}_{d,r}$ are:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}_{d,l} &= \mathbf{p}_l \\ \mathbf{p}_{d,r} &= \mathbf{p}_l + \mathbf{p}_r^l(t_0) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 6. The CENTAURO robot in one of the trial to estimate the mass of a wooden block.

where p_l and p_r are the actual linear position pose of the left and right end-effectors, and $p_r^l(t_0)$ is the pose of the right end-effector with respect to the left one at the time t_0 , which is the instant in which the box is grasped and the user begins to teleoperate the robot. So the elastic element K will generate motions to keep the right end-effector at the same t_0 pose with respect to the left one. As a visual aid, the relevant elements involved in the formulas are shown in Fig. 5. The object velocity command \dot{x}^* can be generated with any kind of teleoperation interface, e.g., the TelePhysicalOperation interface [28], with which the commands are generated from the arm displacements of the operator, tracked with a tracking camera placed on the operator wrist (Fig. 2). Following the concept of our previous work [30], the realization of the commanded object velocity is distributed to the mobile base if the arms of the robot are in a region of low manipulability.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

We have demonstrated our shared control approach for bimanual object transportation with the CENTAURO platform, a dual arm robot equipped with a hybrid leg-wheel mobility system. The robot software architecture is based on the *XBot* middleware [35] and on the *CartesI/O* Control Framework [36].

We have tested the mass estimation procedure 15 times to assess its effectiveness in estimating the mass of an object (Fig. 6). In this experiment, the robot arms are placed at the sides of a wooden block object of $1.958 \pm 0.002kg$. An initial grasping force is reached to allow the object to be firmly lifted. As soon as the lifting phase is completed, the mass of the object is estimated through Eq. (2). The results of the mass estimation trials are shown in Fig. 7. Different initial grasping forces (45N, 40N, 35N) have been established to evaluate the effect of the initial grasping force on the estimation of the mass of the object. From the plots of Fig. 7, we can see that the initial grasping force only slightly influences the mass estimation error. The estimated mass error is lower when the initial grasping force is lower. This may be due to the kinematic differences caused

Fig. 7. Results over 15 trials of the mass estimation of the wooden block. In the top plot, it is displayed the estimation error of each trial; the three different colors represent groups with different initial grasping force set (45N, 40N, 35N). In the bottom plot, they are shown the mean and the standard deviation for each group.

Fig. 8. The setup of the objects picking and transportation experiment. The wooden block (1) must be placed inside the container (2). Then, the container with the block inside must be transported to the final location (3).

by the application of different amounts of forces due to the unmeasured elasticity in the robot structure, despite the encoders registering the same robot configuration used by the force estimation module to estimate the forces from the joint torques in the arms. The results do not indicate a significant influence on the choice of the initial grasping force, verifying the robustness of the approach at different levels of initial grasping forces used during the mass estimation phase. The average error over all the trials has resulted to be $0.074kg$, with a standard deviation of $0.057kg$, resulting in a relative standard error of 3.769%.

In another experiment, grasping and transportation of some objects was performed. We have set up a scenario where the goal is to pick a wooden block, transport it into a plastic container, pick the container with the wooden block inside, and transport them to a desired location (Fig. 8). The execution of the task is divided into different phases, where the teleoperation is combined with some autonomy modes. Some video frames of the experiment are visible in Fig. 9. In a preliminary phase, the robot arms autonomously reach the wooden block. This speeds up the execution of the tasks and relief the operator from precisely position the arms to the object sides. This autonomous way-points reaching is made possible thanks to a vision system that exploits *ArUco* markers¹ to detect the pose of the object, whose dimension

¹http://wiki.ros.org/aruco_detect

Fig. 9. Video frames from the objects picking and transportation experiment. From left to right: (1) the CENTAURO robot is autonomously approaching the block to grasp it; (2) the operator is teleoperating the block inside the plastic container; (3) the robot is grasping the plastic container, estimating its weight and computing a grasping force; (4) the operator is placing the container to the final location.

is assumed to be known for the pose detection. Once the two arms are placed to the sides of the box, the box is lifted with an initial grasping force set to $45N$ applied to lift firmly the object during the mass estimation phase as described in Section III. The robot estimates the mass of the object and derives the required grasping force \bar{f} that is used to command the grasping forces at the necessary level to maintain the grasp without the application of unnecessary higher forces. Following this, the robot is ready to accept user commands to transport the object to the desired location, while keeping the grasping force at the desired value computed from the estimated mass, using Eq. (6). For large displacements of the mobile base, the user can choose to command the mobile base directly (Fig. 2). Once the object is placed inside the plastic container, the same autonomous pick-up procedure and grasping force computation are executed for the container, which is then transported teleoperating the robot to the final location.

During this experiment, the two object masses estimated with Eq. (2) resulted in $2.111kg$ for the wooden block and $2.671kg$ for the container with the block inside (with respect to a real value of $1.958 \pm 0.002kg$ and $2.63 \pm 0.004kg$). For simplicity, the static friction coefficient μ_s has been set equal for the material pairs end-effector-wood and end-effector-plastic to 0.6. The required grasping forces \bar{f} (Eq. (5)) were $24.16N$ and $30.57N$, considering a safety margin gain k of 1.4. In the control law of Eq. (6), the parameters have been experimentally tuned to adjust the sensitivity of the robot generated motions: the diagonal elements of \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{K} were set to 2500 and 200 respectively. The rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_b is updated at each control loop accordingly to the position of the two end-effectors, considering the frame $\langle b \rangle$ as a frame with the y axis always aligned with the line of conjunction of the two contact points.

The relevant plots are shown in Fig. 10, Fig. 11 and Fig. 12. All plots present two different colored areas: in the first area, the mass estimation and the grasping force computation are performed, while in the second area the robot is teleoperated. In all figures, the plot on the left refers to the grasping and transportation of the wooden block,

whereas the plot on the right refers to the grasping and transportation of the plastic container with the wooden block inside. In Fig. 10, the sensed forces at the end-effectors ${}^b\mathbf{f}_{s,l}$ and ${}^b\mathbf{f}_{s,r}$ (rotated according to the object frame $\langle b \rangle$) are shown. It can be noticed that the grasping forces (y_{left} and y_{right}) in the first colored area reach the initial grasping force set ($\pm 45N$); whereas in the second colored area they are kept as much as possible equal to the required grasping force value \bar{f} ($\pm 24.16N$ for the block and $\pm 30.57N$ for the container with the block inside). At the very end of the left plot, an increase in the sensed forces can be noticed. These are caused by a collision with the plastic container when the wooden block is placed inside. Other smaller deviations of the grasping forces from the desired references are due to the user object velocity commands, shown in the first rows of Fig. 11. In this figure the velocities commanded to the mobile base directly by the operator are shown in the second row. According to the manipulability level of the arms [30], the commanded object velocities are scaled down (third row) and the locomotion velocities are generated (fourth row). In Fig. 12, the Cartesian velocities of the end-effectors are plotted. Please note that these Cartesian velocities have been computed from the derivation of the robot joint positions, hence they have been post-processed with a moving average filter to reduce the noise and to improve the visualization for the reader.

The grasping and transportation experiment described has been recorded and shown in the video attached with this paper, also available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7s1n0weq5To>.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In our previous works, we have demonstrated our novel teleoperation interface, the TelePhysicalOperation concept [28], and we have shown how autonomy modules can help in the execution of a task, assisting the human operator and improving the task execution performance [30]. Following the idea of the shared control locomanipulation, in this work we have presented an additional module to face the bimanual pick and place challenge of objects of unknown mass. By combining local robot autonomy and teleoperation,

Fig. 10. Left and right end-effectors sensed forces during the objects picking and transportation experiment. The left plot is referred to the wooden block pick and place sub-task, the right plot to the plastic container pick and place sub-task. The two colored areas in each plot represent the different phases: in the first area, the mass is estimated and the grasping force \bar{f} is computed; in the second area, the control law of Eq. (6) is applied and the operator can send the commands. The autonomy feature is taking care of maintaining the grasping force to the desired value calculated (represented by the dotted black horizontal line).

Fig. 11. Inputs data for the objects picking and transportation experiment. Left and right images represent the data gathered during the pick and place sub-task of the wooden block and the plastic container respectively. The colored areas represent the different phases: in the first area, the mass is estimated and the grasping force \bar{f} is computed; in the second area, the control law of Eq. (6) is applied and the operator can send the commands. In the first and second row they are displayed the operator commands relative to the object and to the robot body, respectively. Accordingly to the arm manipulability level, the commanded velocities represented in the first row are scaled down (third row) and robot body velocity commands generated (fourth row).

Fig. 12. End-effectors Cartesian velocities during the objects picking and transportation experiment. Left and right images represent the data gathered during the pick and place sub-task of the wooden block and the plastic container respectively. The colored areas represent the different phases: in the first area, the mass is estimated and the grasping force \bar{f} is computed; in the second area, the control law of Eq. (6) is applied and the operator can send the commands. The data is computed from the sensed joint positions, hence filtered with a moving average to improve the visualization reducing the noise.

the bimanual object picking and transportation task can be effectively accomplished in a shared control manner.

We rely on the (estimated) sensed forces at the end-effectors to estimate the object mass and to compute a required grasping force. In a similar way as humans do in front of an unknown mass, the robot is able to derive the required grasping force in order to exert a sufficient amount of “squeezing” force to prevent the object from falling while at the same time not exerting unnecessary high forces on the object. The proposed bimanual object picking and transportation control interface allows the operator to command object velocities, while ensuring the grasping of the object imposing the grasping force at the desired value. This results in a safe object transportation, relieving the operator from taking care of the forces applied on the object in order to maintain the bimanual grasp.

Experimental validations were performed with the CEN-TAURO robotic platform involving the bimanual picking and transportation of objects of different masses and sizes, showing the adaptability of the proposed method.

Future works will consider other constraints on the arms motions, like keeping a desired object orientation. More dynamic tasks will be addressed, such as the case of adding additional objects inside a container while the robot is transporting it. Other kinds of bimanual tasks may be studied, e.g. for manipulating heavy tools that need at the same time to interact and to apply forces to the environment to perform a task.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. C. Kemp, A. Edsinger, and E. Torres-Jara, “Challenges for robot manipulation in human environments [grand challenges of robotics],” *IEEE Robot. Automat. Mag.*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 20–29, 2007.
- [2] N. Kashiri *et al.*, “CENTAURO: A hybrid locomotion and high power resilient manipulation platform,” *IEEE Robot. Autom. Lett.*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 1595–1602, 2019.
- [3] T. Asfour *et al.*, “ARMAR-6: A high-performance humanoid for human-robot collaboration in real-world scenarios,” *IEEE Robot. Automat. Mag.*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 108–121, 2019.
- [4] J. F. Buhl *et al.*, “A dual-arm collaborative robot system for the smart factories of the future,” *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 38, pp. 333–340, 2019.
- [5] C. Smith, Y. Karayiannidis, L. Nalpanidis, X. Gratal, P. Qi, D. V. Dimarogonas, and D. Kragic, “Dual arm manipulation—a survey,” *Robot. and Auton. Syst.*, vol. 60, no. 10, pp. 1340–1353, 2012.
- [6] M. Uchiyama and P. Dauchez, “A symmetric hybrid position/force control scheme for the coordination of two robots,” in *IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Automat.*, vol. 1, 1988, pp. 350–356.
- [7] K. Benali, J.-F. Brethé, F. Guérin, and M. Gorka, “Dual arm robot manipulator for grasping boxes of different dimensions in a logistics warehouse,” in *IEEE Int. Conf. Ind. Technol.*, 2018, pp. 147–152.
- [8] T. Wimböck and C. Ott, *Dual-Arm Manipulation*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2012, pp. 353–366.
- [9] M. Bjerkeng, J. Schrimpf, T. Myhre, and K. Y. Pettersen, “Fast dual-arm manipulation using variable admittance control: Implementation and experimental results,” in *IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. Intell. Robots Syst.*, 2014, pp. 4728–4734.
- [10] S. Tarbouriech, B. Navarro, P. Fraitse, A. Crosnier, A. Cherubini, and D. Sallé, “Admittance control for collaborative dual-arm manipulation,” in *Int. Conf. Adv. Robot.*, 2019, pp. 198–204.
- [11] M. Lei, M. Selvaggio, T. Wang, F. Ruggiero, C. Zhou, C. Yao, and Y. Zheng, “Dual-arm object transportation via model predictive control and external disturbance estimation,” in *IEEE Int. Conf. Autom. Sci. Eng.*, 2022.
- [12] P. Chiacchio, S. Chiaverini, and B. Siciliano, “Direct and inverse kinematics for coordinated motion tasks of a two-manipulator system,” *J. Dynamic Syst. Meas. Control*, vol. 118, no. 4, pp. 691–697, 1996.
- [13] F. Caccavale, P. Chiacchio, and S. Chiaverini, “Task-space regulation of cooperative manipulators,” *Automatica*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 879–887, 2000.
- [14] B. V. Adorno, P. Fraitse, and S. Druon, “Dual position control strategies using the cooperative dual task-space framework,” in *IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. Intell. Robots Syst.*, 2010, pp. 3955–3960.
- [15] H. A. Park and C. S. G. Lee, “Extended cooperative task space for manipulation tasks of humanoid robots,” in *IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Autom.*, 2015, pp. 6088–6093.
- [16] R. S. Jamisola and R. G. Roberts, “A more compact expression of relative jacobian based on individual manipulator jacobians,” *Robot. and Auton. Syst.*, vol. 63, pp. 158–164, 2015.
- [17] M. Selvaggio, M. Cagnetti, S. Nikolaidis, S. Ivaldi, and B. Siciliano, “Autonomy in physical human-robot interaction: A brief survey,” *IEEE Robot. Autom. Lett.*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 7989–7996, 2021.
- [18] M. Laghi, M. Maimeri, M. Marchand, C. Leparoux, M. Catalano, A. Ajoudani, and A. Bicchi, “Shared-autonomy control for intuitive bimanual tele-manipulation,” in *IEEE-RAS Int. Conf. Humanoid Robots*, 2018, pp. 1–9.
- [19] D. Rakita, B. Mutlu, M. Gleicher, and L. M. Hiatt, “Shared control-based bimanual robot manipulation,” *Science Robotics*, vol. 4, no. 30, 2019.
- [20] D. Ortenzi, R. Muthusamy, A. Freddi, A. Monteriù, and V. Kyriki, “Dual-arm cooperative manipulation under joint limit constraints,” *Robot. and Auton. Syst.*, vol. 99, pp. 110–120, 2018.
- [21] M. Faroni, M. Beschi, A. Visioli, and L. Molinari Tosatti, “A global approach to manipulability optimisation for a dual-arm manipulator,” in *Int. Conf. Emerg. Technol. Factory Autom.*, 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [22] R. Pi, P. Cieślak, P. Ridaou, and P. J. Sanz, “Twinbot: Autonomous underwater cooperative transportation,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 37 668–37 684, 2021.
- [23] N. Mavrakis and R. Stolkin, “Estimation and exploitation of objects’ inertial parameters in robotic grasping and manipulation: A survey,” *Robot. and Auton. Syst.*, vol. 124, p. 103374, 2020.
- [24] J. Wu, I. Yildirim, J. J. Lim, B. Freeman, and J. Tenenbaum, “Galileo: Perceiving physical object properties by integrating a physics engine with deep learning,” in *Advances Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 28, 2015.
- [25] E. Krotkov, R. Klatzky, and N. Zumel, “Robotic perception of material: Experiments with shape-invariant acoustic measures of material type,” in *Experimental Robotics IV*, O. Khatib and J. K. Salisbury, Eds. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 1997, pp. 204–211.
- [26] Y. Yu, K. Fukuda, and S. Tsujio, “Estimation of mass and center of mass of graspless and shape-unknown object,” in *IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Autom.*, vol. 4, 1999, pp. 2893–2898 vol.4.
- [27] A. Marino, G. Muscio, and F. Pierri, “Distributed cooperative object parameter estimation and manipulation without explicit communication,” in *IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Autom.*, 2017, pp. 2110–2116.
- [28] D. Torielli, L. Muratore, A. Laurenzi, and N. Tsagarakis, “Telephysicaloperation: Remote robot control based on a virtual “marionette” type interaction interface,” *IEEE Robot. Autom. Lett.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 2479–2486, 2022.
- [29] A. Billard and D. Kragic, “Trends and challenges in robot manipulation,” *Science*, vol. 364, no. 6446, 2019.
- [30] D. Torielli, L. Muratore, and N. Tsagarakis, “Manipulability-aware shared locomotion motion generation for teleoperation of mobile manipulators,” in *IEEE Int. Conf. Intell. Robots Syst.*, 2022.
- [31] S. L. Chiu, “Task compatibility of manipulator postures,” *Int. J. Robot. Res.*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 13–21, 1988.
- [32] S. Haddadin, A. De Luca, and A. Albu-Schäffer, “Robot collisions: A survey on detection, isolation, and identification,” *IEEE Trans. Robot.*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 1292–1312, 2017.
- [33] M. T. Francomano, D. Accoto, and E. Guglielmelli, “Artificial sense of slip—a review,” *IEEE Sensors J.*, vol. 13, no. 7, pp. 2489–2498, 2013.
- [34] N. Morita, H. Nogami, E. Higurashi, and R. Sawada, “Grasping force control for a robotic hand by slip detection using developed micro laser doppler velocimeter,” *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 2, 2018.
- [35] L. Muratore, A. Laurenzi, E. Mingo Hoffman, and N. Tsagarakis, “The XBot real-time software framework for robotics: From the developer to the user perspective,” *IEEE Robot. Autom. Mag.*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 133–143, 2020.
- [36] A. Laurenzi, E. M. Hoffman, L. Muratore, and N. Tsagarakis, “Cartesi/O: A ROS Based Real-Time Capable Cartesian Control Framework,” in *IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Autom.*, 2019, pp. 591–596.